

An Adaptive Real-Time Digital Twin for Stand-Alone and Joint Inversion of Electromagnetic and Magnetic Data

SAGEEP

Applications of AI to Geophysics Session
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Overview and Impacts

Overview:

- Part of a project funded by ARPA-E (Advanced Research Project Agency-Energy) within the U.S. Department of Energy
- **Objective:** Combine geophysical methods, artificial intelligence, and cloud computing to support powerline undergrounding

Impacts:

- Enhanced (near) real-time 3D imaging of earth
- Applications ranging from utility undergrounding, resource exploration (like critical mineral, ground water), environmental monitoring, agriculture, and national security

This talk focuses on 3D Digital Twin for standalone and joint inversion for EM and magnetic data

R. Amzi Jeffs' presentation focuses on GPR data

Lal Mamud's presentation focuses on metal detector data

1. Develop AI-based real-time 3D inversion of EM, magnetic, GPR, and metal detector data

2. Develop AI-based real-time anomaly detection and classification

3. AI-based uncertainty quantification in inversion and detection/classification

4. AI-enabled Digital Twin for stand-alone/joint inversion

5. Integration of AI algorithms and augmented reality (AR) with cloud platform

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Motivations: To Support Undergrounding

- U.S. has over **5.5 million** line-miles of overhead powerline and more than **180 million power poles**
- These overhead systems are **highly susceptible to damage** from weather events and tree-related incidents, which account for **60-70% power outages**
- **Undergrounding power lines** is a proven way to enhance system security and reliability, both for **distribution lines** (local networks) and **transmission lines** (log-distance networks)
- **Geophysical methods** are essential to provide **subsurface maps** that identify rocks, existing utilities, boulders, and other obstacle to **prevent hazardous and costly damage** during underground installation
- However, **current processing and reporting workflows** can take **weeks to months** to deliver subsurface maps, thus **causing significant delays**

This project aims to provide subsurface images/maps in (near) real-time

Geophysical Imaging

- Buried objects (e.g., utility pipelines, boulders, metallic bodies, bedrock, cavities/sinkholes) create geophysical data anomaly at the surface
- Process and invert geophysical data to image the subsurface
- Classical methods use optimization algorithms, mostly utilizing gradient-based methods, such as steepest-descent, conjugate-gradient or Gauss-Newton methods
- Traditional inversion methods are **computationally expensive** and **may require hours or even days of computations**
- Even more challenging for 3D inversion, **not feasible for real-time inversion**

Geophysical Data Acquisition

Processing & Inversion

Image source: SimPEG

<https://simpeg.xyz/user-tutorials/inv-magnetics-induced-3d>

AI-enabled algorithms for data inversion

- Framework are being developed using advanced AI/ML algorithms to instantaneously analyze various geophysical data (electromagnetic, magnetic, ground penetrating radar, and metal detector – EM, Mag, GPR, and MD)
- Developing AI algorithms to:
 - ✓ predict distribution of subsurface properties (like traditional geophysical inversion) in real time
 - ✓ Detect and classify anomalies in real time
 - ✓ Uncertainty quantification
 - ✓ Digital Twin for standalone inversion and joint inversion
- Integrating data management and AI processing with AWS cloud platform for web access and AR/VR visualization

Anomaly detection/classification:

Utility pipes, boulders, metallic bodies etc.

Overall concept

AI-enabled Digital Twin

- Combines real-time 3D inversion, anomaly detection, anomaly classification, and uncertainty quantification in a unified framework
- Acts as standalone inversion tool for single modal geophysical data, or joint inversion tool for multimodal geophysical data
- Updates its performance over time as new/improved information available
- Continuously refines subsurface images as new datasets become available

Detection: anomaly detection/segmentation and anomaly classification

Results: Spherical Body (Magnetic Data)

True Susceptibility

True Mask

Inverted Susceptibility

Predicted Mask

Standard Deviation

Magnetic Data

Classification: sphere

Precision: 99.1%
Recall: 85.3 %

Results: Spherical Body (EM Data)

True Conductivity

True Mask

Inverted Conductivity

Predicted Mask

Standard Deviation

EM Data

Classification: sphere

Precision: 91.1%
Recall: 99.5%

Results: Spherical Body (Mag & EM Data)

True Susceptibility

True Conductivity

True Mask

Inverted Susceptibility

Inverted Conductivity

Predicted Mask

Standard Deviation

Magnetic & EM Data

Digital twin algorithm

Classification: sphere

Precision: 95.8%
Recall: 99.7%

Results: Two Objects (Magnetic Data)

True Susceptibility

True Mask

Inverted Susceptibility

Predicted Mask

Standard Deviation

Magnetic Data

Classification: multi objects

Precision: 95.6%
Recall: 83.3%

Results: Two Objects (EM Data)

True Conductivity

True Mask

Inverted Conductivity

Predicted Mask

Standard Deviation

EM Data

Digital twin algorithm

Classification: multi objects

Precision: 89.7%
Recall: 92.6%

Results: Two Objects (Mag & EM Data)

True Susceptibility

True Conductivity

True Mask

Inverted Susceptibility

Inverted Conductivity

Predicted Mask

Standard Deviation

Magnetic & EM Data

Digital twin
algorithm

Classification: multi objects

Precision: 95.1%
Recall: 92.6%

Quantitative Results: thousands of test data

Using only magnetic surveys

Accuracy	FNR	FPR	Precision	Recall
99.69%	19.85%	0.09%	91.09%	80.15%

Using only electromagnetic surveys

Accuracy	FNR	FPR	Precision	Recall
99.80%	7.54%	0.12%	89.96%	92.46%

Using both surveys

Accuracy	FNR	FPR	Precision	Recall
99.87%	5.65%	0.07%	94.16%	94.35%

FNR: False Negative Rate
FPR: False Positive Rate

Conclusions

- Real-time 3D Digital Twin for mapping near surface infrastructure using geophysical methods
- Acts as standalone or joint inversion engine
- Predicts distribution of physical properties, detect/classify anomalies, and quantify uncertainty

Next Step:

- Cross-gradient constraints to jointly invert multimodal geophysical data

Thank You!

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